

Mass Spectral Investigation on some Substituted 4-Aminooxanes

K SLLVARAJ^a, N CHANDRASEKARA^b and K RAMARAJAN^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore-641 014

^bDepartment of Chemistry, CBM College, Coimbatore-641 042

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A systematic investigation on the mass spectral behaviour of saturated six-membered heterocyclic ring systems containing primary amino group has not been undertaken so far. We report herein the mass spectral analysis of 2,6-diphenyl-4-aminooxanes (1-9). The fragmentation pathways followed by these compounds may be understood by considering the mass spectral behaviour of the aminooxane (5), chosen as a representative example. The major fragmentation pathways which the molecular ion of 5 undergoes have been shown in Scheme 1.

In the case of 2-alkyloxanes the predominant fragmentation process was observed to be an α -

1. R₁= H, R₂= H, R₃= NH₂, R₄= H.
2. R₁= H, R₂= NH₂, R₃= H, R₄= H.
3. R₁= CH₃, R₂= H, R₃= NH₂, R₄= H.
4. R₁= CH₃, R₂= NH₂, R₃= H, R₄= H.
5. R₁= C₂H₅, R₂= H, R₃= NH₂, R₄= H.
6. R₁= C₂H₅, R₂= NH₂, R₃= H, R₄= H.
7. R₁= CH₃, R₂= H, R₃= NH₂, R₄= CH₃.
8. R₁= CH₃, R₂= NH₂, R₃= H, R₄= CH₃.

Scheme 1 Mass fragmentation of compound 5

cleavage between the ring carbon and the alkyl substituent, resulting in a *M*-alkyl fragment¹. However, no similar cleavage between the ring carbon and aryl group (at C-2 or C-6) was observed in our system.

A cleavage, marked 'a', across the ring gives rise to the peaks at *m/z* 148, as evidenced by the presence of a metastable peak at *m/z* 78 [(148)²/281 = 77.9], and at *m/z* 133 (*m** = 63). Similar fragmentation takes place for other compounds as well. Expulsion of Ph-CH=CH-C₂H₅ as a neutral species from the molecular ion results in the formation of an oxetan at *m/z* 149 (*m** = 79). Successive losses of PhCHO and H and separately of HCONH₂ and H gives rise to the peaks at *m/z* 43, 42, 104 and 103, respectively. A cleavage, marked 'b', across the ring results in the peaks at *m/z* 120 (*m** = 51) and 161 (*m** = 92). Loss of formyl radical (involving hydrogen migration) from the former and of NH₂ radical from the latter explains the peaks at *m/z* 91 and 145, respectively. The peak at *m/z* 85, though insignificant (1%), results from the cleavage, marked 'c', across the ring (*m** = 26). A loss of ethyl radical could well explain the formation of the base peak at *m/z* 56.

The peaks at *m/z* 106 and 104 are produced straightaway from the molecular ion (*m** at = 40 and 38, respectively). A loss of H from each of them explains the respective peaks at *m/z* 105 and 103. A loss of H from the neutral species of molecular weight 175 could easily rationalise the formation of the peak at *m/z* 104. But the appearance of a metastable peak at *m/z* 108 regates this possibility. The formation of this peak (*m/z* 104) thus remains intriguing.

All the fragmentation pathways described above, are common for all the compounds studied. The peaks at *m/z* 43, 65, 77, 104 and 105 may arise from more than one species and require no elaboration.

Experimental

The aminooxanes (**1-9**) were synthesised following literature procedure². The electron impact mass spectral data (70 eV) were collected on CEC 21 HR unit.

The *m/z* values and relative abundances (within parentheses) of the various peaks observed in the MS of the compounds **1-9** are as follows : **1** *m/z* 253 (*M** 19%) 149(7) 133(44), 120(2), 117(17), 106(23), 105(100), 104(50), 103(14), 91(12), 77(30), 57(2), 56(9), 43(84) and 42(28); **2** *m/z* 253 (*M** 13%), 149(1) 133(13), 120(2), 106(24), 105(26), 104(100), 103(13) 91(9), 77(23), 57(1), 56(5), 43(84) and 42(14); **3** *m/z* 267 (*M** 14%), 149(16), 147(19), 134(7), 133(17), 131(48), 120(2), 106(38), 105(81), 104(30), 103(12), 91(28), 77(39), 71(6), 57(100), 56(35), 43(35) and 42(14); **4** *m/z* 267 (*M** 4%), 149(1), 147(8), 134(2), 133(6), 131(2), 120(2), 106(21), 105(20), 104(21), 103(8), 91(17), 77(21), 71(2), 57(100), 56(22), 43(29) and 42(7); **5** *m/z* 281 (*M** 10%), 161(8), 149(13), 148(58), 145(37), 133(23), 120(3), 106(44), 105(88), 104(32), 103(12), 91(42), 85(6) 77(46), 56(100), 43(46) and 42(18); **6** *m/z* 281 (*M** 4%), 161(7), 149(4), 148(6), 145(4), 133(18), 132(100), 120(1), 106(26), 105(19), 104(19), 103(8), 91(24), 85(3), 77(19), 56(68), 43(34) and 42(7); **7** *m/z* 281 (*M** 7%), 163(5), 134(3), 131(2), 118(100), 177(25), 106(7), 105(11), 91(18), 77(11), 57(30) and 56(10); **8** *m/z* 281 (*M** 5%), 163(2), 147(2), 134(1), 131(1), 118(100), 117(25), 105(5), 105(8), 91(19), 77(13), 57(55) and 56(11); **9** *m/z* 253 (*M** 21), 149(10), 133(60), 120(1), 117(15), 106(27), 105(100), 104(93), 103(22), 91(16), 77(44), 57(8), 56(2), 43(88) and 42(26).

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